

TOXICITY OF METALS IN VITAL ORGANS OF THE BODY AND THE STUDY OF STRATEGIES FOR ELIMINATING THEIR TOXINS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF RHAZES AND AVICENNA

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Introduction and Objective: In recent decades, due to the expansion of the consumption of processed foods, the increase in environmental pollutants, and the decline in nutritional quality, the possibility of poisoning with some metals found in foods, such as lead and mercury, has increased. These metals can negatively affect vital organs of the body, such as the brain, heart, and liver, disrupting their function. The present study aimed to investigate how metal toxicity occurs in vital organs of the body and analyze the therapeutic strategies for eliminating their toxins from the perspectives of Rhazes and Avicenna in two valuable books, *Al-Hawi fi al-Tibb* and *Al-Qanun fi al-Tibb*.

Method: This library research was conducted using a descriptive-analytical method and a historical approach.

Results: Rhazes and Avicenna consider the amount of heavy and semi-heavy metals in food, such as lead, mercury, arsenic, and antimony, to be harmful to health and, in some cases, fatal. They say about lead toxicity: "Lead makes the brain ponderous and causes indolence of intellect and weakness of movement. Lead also causes blockage in the liver and spleen." Rhazes says about mercury poisoning: "It causes anxiety and tremors in the limbs," and Avicenna writes about arsenic toxicity: "If used without care, it corrupts the blood and its effect also reaches the liver and heart, causing death or severe disability in the body." To treat metal poisoning, these two Iranian scientists used methods such as cleansing the digestive tract by inducing vomiting and using laxatives and enemas, and to purify the blood, using diuretics and diaphoretics, and to neutralize toxins, using mteriamedica, as well as natural antidotes.

Conclusion: Research shows that there are natural antidotes in nature, and new scientific evidence confirms their positive effects. Given that many of these natural compounds do not have side effects at low doses and are on the list of generally safe compounds, they can be used as antidotes for some metal toxins in food with further testing.

Keywords: Antidote, Vital Organs, Metal Toxicity, Rhazes, Avicenna, History of Medicine.